

Work Profile of the Weavers in Handloom Industry

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the research paper is to analyse the work profile of handloom weavers and to provide some appropriate suggestions for uplifting the working conditions. The study has been undertaken to find out means to revive the traditional handloom industries. The study mainly depends upon primary as well as secondary data. Primary data has been collected from 80 respondents using interview schedule. The study found that poverty is the main reason for choosing weaving as their occupation. It is suggested that government should increase the benefits for the member of the handloom cooperative society to attract all weavers under its fold and it concludes that there is many experienced handloom weavers available in Kanniyakumari District.

Keywords: *Weavers, revive and cooperative society*

Objectives of the study

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Statement of the problem

The handloom weavers have been very badly affected by the adoption of power-loom sector. The membership strength of handloom cooperative societies has been decreasing due to power loom sector. The capital base of these societies has been eroded. The people who faced to leave the co-operative society due to such competition suffer psychologically as well as economically. The people who are working in the handloom industry do not prefer to continue for long due to competition of power loom sector. The handloom weavers are subjected to so many problems.

There is trimendores decline in the handloom industry due to the above factors. Considering the above facts, the present study has been undertaken by the researcher to find out means to revive the traditional handloom industries particularly in Kanniyakumari District.

Methodology

The study mainly depends upon primary as well as secondary data. Primary data has been collected from 80 respondents using interview schedule. Through interview schedule researchers analyze the year of experience, membership in society, health hazards in occupation, working condition, mode of payment and reason to select the job of the respondents. Secondary data were collected from books, journal, magazines and reports. As census method is not possible to collect the primary data within stipulated period convenience sampling method was used for collecting the data.

Years of Experience

Experience refers to the number of years worked. Experience makes the person expert and improves their knowledge in particular field of work.

Table No: 1**Years of experience – wise distribution in sample respondents**

Sl.No	Years of experience	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Up to 10 years	10	12.5
2	11-20 years	22	27.5
3	21-30 years	18	22.5
4	Above 30 years	30	37.5
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

From the table 1, it is seen that 37.5 percent of the respondents have work experience more than 30 years; 27.5 percent respondents have 11 to 20 years of experience; 22.5 percent respondents have 21 to 30 years experience and 12.5 percent of the respondents have below 10 years experience. This indicates that these weavers were working in handloom industry for a long period of time.

Membership in Society

Person with own looms or without looms and has knowledge about weaving can join as member into cooperative society. They must be eligible for membership in cooperative society by satisfying conditions provided by it.

Table No: 2**Membership in society – wise distribution in sample respondents**

Sl.No	Membership in society	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	32	40
2	No	48	60
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

Above table 2 shows that 40 percentage of the respondents are members in the society. Rest of 60 percentage respondents are not members in cooperative society as it provides low wages when compare to private weavers.

Number of years as member in the society

Some of the respondent weavers i.e. 32 of the total respondent have membership in cooperative society. Year wise distribution of the sample respondents is shown below.

Table No: 3**Number of years as member in the society**

Sl.No	No of years	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 10 years	17	53.1
2	10-15 years	12	37.5
3	Above 15 years	3	9.4
Total		32	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3 shows that 53.1percent of the respondents have experience less than 10 years in the cooperative society, 37.5 percentage respondents have experience from 10 to 15 years and 9.4percent of the sample respondents have experience above 15 years in the cooperative society.

Health hazards in occupation

There is possibility for accident during the work in any occupation. But in hand loom industry chances for accident is very low when compared with other job but there is chances for physical strains and also mental stress it is also consider as hazard.

Table No: 4**Health hazard in occupation of the sample respondents**

Sl. No	Health hazard	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	21	26.3
2	No	59	73.8
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

Table 4 exhibits that out of 80 sample respondents only 26.3 percent respondents have affected by health hazards and 73.8 percent of the respondents are not affected by any health hazards such as wound, muscle pain and the like, as it is not dangerous or hazardous work compared to other industries.

Hours of working

There is no prescribed time limit for the people working under private handloom. In cooperative society also, workers are not compelled to work for particular prescribed time. In order to find that working hours the respondents are asked to give their working hours and is shown below.

Table No: 5**Working time in hand loom industry**

Sl. No	Hours of working	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Up to 6	37	46.3
2	7 hours	23	28.8
3	8 hours	9	11.3
4	Above 9 hours	11	13.8
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

The above table reveals that 46.3 percent respondents are working up to 6 hours 28.8 percent respondents are working up to 7 hours. 11.3 percent respondents are in the 8 hours work group and 13.8 percent respondents are in the above 9 hours work group. It is considered as overtime, because according to Indian law normal working hour is 8 hours per day.

Satisfaction regarding working condition

Man has to exert his energy both mentally and physically. The opportunities and provisions are available for working essentially exertion of energy either physically or mentally for a reward. They include natural environment and working system etc. Workers should be satisfied with their working condition to improve productivity.

Table No: 6**Satisfaction regarding working condition of the sample respondents**

Sl.No	Satisfied	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Satisfied	78	97.5
2	Not satisfied	2	2.5
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

It is observed from table 6 that out of 80 sample respondents 97.5 percent respondents are satisfied and 2.5 percent respondents are not satisfied with their working condition.

Mode of payment

Handloom weavers may get income in the way of wages or by the way of salary. Wages means getting income on daily or weekly basis where as salary means getting income on monthly basis.

Table No: 7**Mode of payment –wise distribution in sample respondents**

Sl. No	Mode of payment	Number of respondents	percentage
1	Daily wages	47	58.8
2	Weekly wages	33	41.2
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

This table 7 indicates that 58.8 percentage workers are getting daily wages and 41.2 percentage workers are getting wages on weekly basis. People need money to manage daily expenses, but poor people cannot afford it without daily wages. That is why, weavers are getting their wages on daily basis.

Reason for choosing handloom work

Several factors may lead the people to select the particular kind of job, but there should be a reason behind the selection of each job.

Table No: 8**Reason for choosing handloom work by the sample respondents**

Sl. No	Reason	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Poverty	37	46.3
2	Unemployment	15	18.8
3	Additional income	6	7.5
4	Time passing	10	12.5
5	Traditional work	9	11.3
6	Willingness to do	3	3.8
Total		80	100

Source: Primary data

From the table 8, it is revealed that poverty is the main contributory factor for choosing weaving as their profession 46.3 percent and followed by unemployment 18.8 percent. 12.5 percent of the sample respondents are doing this work for time pass and 11.3 percent of the respondents choosing it as it is traditional work. Only 7.5 percent of the total respondents carry on handloom weaving to earn more income as their existing income is not enough to overcome their all family needs. Remaining 3.8 percent of the respondents are involving in this work as they are willing to work in handloom industry.

Findings

Majority i.e., 37.5 percent of the respondents have working experience above 30 years; and only 12.5 percent of the respondents are having below 10 years experience. It indicates that these weavers were working in handloom industry for a long period of time. Majority i.e., 40 percent of the respondents are members in the society. Rest of 60 percentage respondents are not members in cooperative society, because it provides low wages when compare to private weavers. Majority i.e., 53.1percent of the sample respondents have experience less than 10 years in the society, and only 9.4percent respondents have experience above 15 years in the cooperative society. Out of 80 sample respondents only 26.3 percentage respondents have affected by health hazards such as wound, muscle pain and the like, as it is not dangerous or hazardous work compared to other industries. Majority i.e., 46.3 percent respondents are working up to 6 hours; and 13.8 percent respondents are in the above 9 hours work group as over time working people. Out of 80 sample respondents 97.5 percent respondents are satisfied with their working condition and 2.5 percent respondents are not satisfied. 58.8 percentage workers are getting daily wages and 41.2 percentage workers are getting wages on weekly basis. People need money to manage daily expenses, but poor people cannot afford it without daily wages. That is why; weavers are getting their wages on daily basis. Poverty is the main contributory factor for choosing weaving as their occupation 46.3 percent and followed by unemployment 18.8 percent Remaining 3.8 percent of the respondents are involving in this work as they are willing to work in handloom industry.

Suggestions

Even cooperative society is providing low wages when compare to private weavers, it provides good working environment, constant work, secured income and many government benefits through implementing schemes. Each and every handloom weavers should come under the roof of cooperative society. Government should increase the benefits for the member of the handloom cooperative society to attract all weavers under its fold.

Conclusion

Handloom weaving activity plays an active role in the growth process of the state as well as the nation. This sector has been considered important because of the traditional artisan craft skills of the weavers which meet the local needs and demands. The study concludes that there is many experienced handloom weavers available in Kanniyakumari District. It also concludes that handloom industry is not hazardous industry to work and it helps to manage daily expenses of the family.

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